

CODIFICATION OF BORROWED WORDS IN UZBEK DICTIONARIES

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Annotation. This article discusses borrowing words in Modern English and Uzbek. It also deals with the problems of codifications of borrowing words in Uzbek dictionaries.

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The great number of borrowings in English left some imprint upon the language. The first effect of foreign influence is observed in the volume of its vocabulary. Due to its history the English language, more than any other modern language, has absorbed foreign elements in its vocabulary. But the adoption of foreign words must not be understood as mere quantitative change. Any importation into the lexical system brings about semantic and stylistic changes in the words of this language and changes in its synonymic groups.

It has been mentioned that when borrowed words were identical in meaning with those already in English the adopted word very often displaced the native word. In most cases, the borrowed words and synonymous native words remained in the language, becoming more or less differentiated in meaning and use. For example, the sphere of application and meaning of feed and nourish.

As a result of the differentiation in meaning between synonymous words many native words or words borrowed earlier narrowed their meaning or sphere of application. Thus the word stool of Anglo-Saxon origin, which in old English denoted any article of furniture designed for sitting on, under the influence of the French borrowing chair came to be used as the name for only one kind of furniture.

Another instance of foreign influence upon the semantic structure of some English words is semantic borrowings, i.e. the borrowing of meaning from a word in a foreign language. This often takes place in English words having common roots with some word, in another language. e.g. words pioneer and cadres which are international words have acquired new meanings under the influence of the Russian *nuaseep* and *кадры*. Sometimes English words having

quite different roots. e.g. the political meaning of shock and deviation have come from the Russian ударный and уклон.[1]

The great number of borrowings could not but leave a definite imprint on the morphological structure of words in English. A number of new structural types appeared in the language. This took place when the morphological structure of borrowings, obscured at the time of adoption, became transparent in the courts of time and served as a pattern for new formation.

Among the affixes which can be considered by English some are highly – productive and can combine with native and borrowed items (e.g. reinter, - able, - er, - ism, etc) other are not so productive and combine only with Romantic stems (co-, de-, tran-, -al, - oy, ie, ical, etc). still others are often met with in borrowed words, but do not form any new words in english (-ous, -ive, -ent, etc). All the words in a language make up its vocabulary. The vocabulary of a language increases through two sources: internal and external. Word formation through the internal capabilities of language (by adding and subtracting words); borrowing from dialects is an internal source, borrowing from another language is an external source. As a result of borrowing words from other languages, there is a difference between native words and borrowed words. The words in Uzbek and Turkic are called native words, and words taken from other languages are called borrowed words.

According to Xolmanova, native words in the Uzbek language consists of Turkic words and they have such features like:

- 1) Words beginning with sounds: v, z, l, g, are not Uzbek: lab (lip).
- 2) The words include f, h, 'are not considered Uzbek: bahor (spring), fikr (thought).
- 3) In Uzbek words vowels do not come side by side: soat (hour).
- 4) Uzbek words are homonymous: soch-soch(hair-scatter,splash), tut-tut (mulberry fruit-catch).
- 5) Historical sound changes in Uzbek words are noticeable: yig'och-og'och(like wode-wood), jil-yil(like yeer-year), jilon-yilon-ilon (like snaca-snake-snake)
- 6) consonants in Uzbek (Turkish) words do not come side by side in the same syllable; g'isht (brick), daraxt (tree).

As the vocabulary of a language evolves in response to changes in society, the role of borrowed words in the enrichment of vocabulary plays a primary role. Since the study is about borrowing words, it is appropriate to define what is actually meant by borrowed words. Longman Dictionary of Language defines borrowed word as a word or phrase which has been taken from one language

and used in another language. Linguists such as Fromkin and Rodman define loan words as a process by which one language or dialect takes and incorporates some linguistic elements from another. Haugen states that borrowing is the adoption of a linguistic expression from one language into another language when no term exists for the new object and concept.[2]

According to surveys, the percentage of modern English words derived from each language is 29% from French, 29% from Latin, 26% from German, and 6% from Greek, the rest accounting for 6% . The Uzbek language has been enriching by Persian-Tajik, Arabic, Russian and English languages so far. It should be noted that with the development of science and technology, progress in international relationships among countries increased the domination of some words and their adoption into different languages. Today, in modern Uzbek language, there are number of borrowed words from other languages and most of them are English. In Uzbek linguistics, the views of professors such as Professor Sh. Rakhmatullayev, F. Abdullayev, I. Kochkortoyena, M. Mirtojiev, N. Nurmonov, A. Mahmudov,

N.Nematov, R.Rasulov on lexical-semantic features of borrowings and the factors of borrowing them into the Uzbek language are very noteworthy. The most remarkable research on English borrowings in the Uzbek language is a dissertation “The meaning development of English borrowings in the Uzbek language”(“O‘zbek tilidagi inglizcha o‘zlashma so‘zlarning ma‘no taraqqiyoti”) written by B.Baymatova to obtain a master degree. The researcher analyses lexical and semantic features of borrowing in the Uzbek language, divides them into thematic groups and explains meaning development of them over the years. There are more than 20 languages, which loaned some words into Uzbek language. After Independence, the amount of English words are more and the development of their meaning is unique. This research learns the synonymic character of borrowings with native words. Although naming and function semes are identical, expression semes differ in the following lexemes. The English “business” lexeme is in the Uzbek Explanatory Dictionary [business - work, occupation] any organizational, economic activity that generates income, is for profit and does not contradict the law. The use of this lexeme became more active after independence. In turn, the business lexeme is synonymous with the “tjorat”, “savdo”(trade) lexeme, while the business lexeme is synonymous with the “ishbilarmonlik” lexeme concerning its polysemantic character. Accordingly, the English compound word for businessman are often freely exchanged with “ishbilarmon”, “tadbirkor”.

We can interchangeably use these Uzbek words and English borrowings in Uzbek:

Stress-tushkunlik

Brifing-uchrashuv,yig'in

Pajama-tungi

Skver-hiyobon

Zoopark-hayvonot

Menejer-boshqaruvchi

Interaktiv-interfaol

Reyting-daraja

Keys-portfel

Trening-mashg'ulot

Interview-uchrashuv

Reportyor-muxbir

Fermer-dehqon

Mister-janob

Many words came to Uzbek through Russian and retained the features of that language along with source language's. For example, though borrowings in Uzbek "trening" and "trenirovka" are synonymous words, they have different features including meaning and usage. "Trenirovka" keeps the Russian language features and it is mainly used in sport. Uzbek word "mashg'ulot" is often interchangeably used. "Trening"(taken from training) was adopted directly from English language and it is mostly used in education and other areas.[3] "Trening" is also used with other words together, such as autotrening(in psychology), seminar-trening, o'quv-trening, trening mashg'ulot" (in education). Trening" is an activity of imparting and acquiring skills in all areas while "Trenirovka" is a work-out in sport. "Keys" (taken from "case") is a sticky tight portfolio in Uzbek, whereas English word "case" has more meanings: container, box, frame, cover, suitcase, bag."Reportyor"(reporter from English) a word which came to Uzbek through Russian and possesses Russian phonetic features. It is observed that there are synomymous words: reportyor (an English word adopted through Russian)-muxbir (Arabic word- to report, reporter - 1) an employee who serves as a journalist in the editorial staff, 2) a person who does not work directly in the editorial office, but regularly collaborates creatively in the media, 3) organizer of reports) in modern Uzbek journalism and their usage area is indistinguishable. The meaning of the words "fermer" (taken from English word farmer) and "dehqon" are also almost similar. Here are the definitions of these words to

compare from wiki-dictionaries: a farmer (fermer) is a person engaged in agriculture, raising living organisms for food or raw materials.

The term usually applies to people who do some combination of raising field crops, orchards, vineyards, poultry, or other livestock. A farmer might own the farmed land or might work as a laborer on land owned by others, but in advanced economies, a farmer is usually a farm owner, while employees of the farm are known as farm workers, or farmhands. However, in the not so distant past, a farmer was a person who promotes or improves the growth of (a plant, crop, etc.) by labor and attention, land or crops or raises animals (as livestock or fish). “Dehqons” (Farmers) are social group, a special category of the population whose main occupation is farming. Farmers work in agriculture, own land and other resources, and run their own farms with their own means of production and the labor of family members. The change of their meaning depends on the society development as well. Briefly, their meaning is almost similar. An English word “Mister” and an Arabic word “Janob” exist in Uzbek Explanatory dictionaries. These are the definitions of these words in Uzbek Explanatory dictionaries: “mister”- a word which is used in the meaning of “janob” in England and America; “janob”-1) a form of honoring people, officials or statesmen in the past and present; 2) irony, added to a person’s name. But in English Explanatory dictionaries “mister” has more meanings than in Uzbek Explanatory dictionaries: Mister- men are sometimes addressed as mister, especially by children and especially when the person talking to them does not know their name.(Collins English dictionary); -variant form of Mr, often used humorously or with offensive emphasis (Lexico,Oxford dictionary) so the usage of these 2 words which exist in the same language as an native and borrowing word and whose origins are certainly different, is the same. The lexical structure of a language is constantly evolving in relation to the political, cultural and spiritual life of a society.[4]

Dictionaries are also created in accordance with the political and spiritual views of society. Comparing the usage of business, farmer, case, training, reporter, mister lexemes in the English and Uzbek Languages, it is clear that these words have Uzbek equivalents which goes back to long history and have been using for centuries. However, the interrelation across cultures led to borrow these words from English into Uzbek. English borrowings enter into synonymous, antonymic, homonymous relationships with the words around them. They are in synonymic line with Uzbek native words which have the same meaning regarding their

meaning in the Uzbek language, in contrast they have more meanings in the English language itself.

There are strong historic links between Ukraine and Turkey, where Tatar Crimea sits in between. Crimean Tatars speak nearly the same language as Turks and for centuries Crimea had been an autonomous land within the Ottoman Empire. Great part of southern Crimea had been part of the Ottoman (Turkish) Empire as well. Tatars and Turks had been always in lands. Many of them settled and were absorbed among Ukrainian people. These inter-significant traces in Ukrainian vocabulary. Thus many Ukrainian words were borrowed from Tatar (Turkic) languages. Ukrainian exclamation Hayda! (Go! Let's Go!) derives from Hayda! Haydi! (Go! Move!) (Compare this term in other Turkic languages: Tatar Bashkir *eyoli* and Kyrgyz *ayola*) to drive. While similar Russian exclamations borrowed from Volga Tatar Ukrainian *bohатыr* (hero) also stems from Turkish *buh* (hero) Ukrainian word *hamanets* (wallet) purse was also borrowed from Turkic (*wh*) in Crimean Tatar *hemian* or Chuvash *haman* means leather purse, bag. In Uzbek it is Uyghur it is *Hemian*, in Kazakh (*emian*) and in Turkmen *ham* stands for leather). In that many of these Turkic/Turkish based Ukrainian words are used with stress by us to define their "Ukrainianess", patriotic and national feelings: example the central square called *Maydan Nezalezhnosti* – Independence square, where term "maydan" is Turkic (from Turkish *meydan* - square); or popular national Ukrainian term *Berkut* golden name for special intervention security forces of Ukrainian police and Ukrainian *chigach* was borrowed from Turkic too (from Crimean Tatar) *Cuman burkut-gold*. [5]

As we know, nowadays we can meet and use many new words and terms in our speech. Now we want to give some international economic terms, which have entered into Uzbek language from English along with the Independence.

International economic terms.

- 1- *Aval* - *Аваль* is a person who takes the debtor under his guarantee is considered responsible with debtor for it.
2. *Addendum* - *Аддендум* is a word which informs about possibility to give additions into the agreement.
- 3- *Adjio* - *Аджио* is arising of prices of currency, bills from their nominal prices.
4. *Bonus* - is a price cut of goods of seller in agreement with purchaser.
5. *Bonn* - *бонн* is a short term obligation of sides.
6. *Via* - *виа* a delivery of goods to the place showed way (for example *via London - Tashkent*)

- 7- Gratis - гратис doing of services, things, processes free of charge
8. Debanure - дебентура Certificate of stock-exchange about returning of money fine.
9. Demping - демпинг is a selling of goods with price out in Foreign Trade, they took goods in outing of production costs (it is made to win in competition).
Djirat - жират person who transfers bill of exchange.
Kabotadj - каботаж taking of people and goods from one part of the country via sea.
Clearing - клиринг system of calculation for goods, bills, services, taking into the consideration their obligations and demands. There are clearing of banks and international currency clearings.
13. Penalty пенальти is a payment in breaching agreement.
- "Pull - "пул" is a temporal monopolistic joining-up. Formally keeping independence of economy. Participants of "Pull" divide expenses and profits on beforehand agreed rules.
- Resident - резидент juridical or physical person who lives.
- Rayting - рейтинг prestige; is showing the political, economic interests of person, company and others.
- Refaction - рефакция cutting of prices of goods if doesn't response for qualities of agreement.
- Royalty - роялти bonus, being paid from time to time from calculation of profitable per cent of trading and sailing by agreed license of contract.
- Subvention - субвенция aims at financing pensions, which are separated for local khokimiyat (for example separating of money for building hospitals only).
- Manager - менежер leader or manager of firm, company or bank, hired manager of company.
- Leasing Лизинг taking of cars, equipments, production installations on lease.
- Consulting - консалтинг service which gives advice and qualitative consultation.
- Claims - клеимслар pretensions, claims, demands.
- Dealers дилерлар members of financing stock-exchanges and banks, who deal with selling and purchasing of valuable metals, currency, bills. They could make agreement between brokers, themselves also with clients.
- Denosation - деносация rejection of agreement.
26. Rent - рента regular payment for the use of land.
- Stagflation - стагфляция inflation with decline in productivity.

Deflete - дефляция take action to reduce the amount of money in circulation in order to lower or keep steady the prices of salable goods.

Obligation - облигация promise, duty or condition that shows what action ought to be taken.

Dividend - дивидент payment of a share of profit to shareholders in a business company.

32- Trust - трест a company who has a charge of property in trust or of the business affairs of an institution.

Polis - полис is a ratify document which insure about of agreement of insurance office.

Factoring - факторинг is one type of affairs in financial. It is specially for little and middle firms which are coming in the world market.

Discount - дискант is a percent which have taken in a bank practice by banks.

Hyperinflation - гиперинфляция is a quick inflation of money.

Indecation - индекация in time of quick inflation of money, it need to cover accumulation and to raise sums.

Agrofirma агрофирма is an institution which grew some kinds of agricultural goods and decline them in cultural style.

Inovation - инновация to find news and to show affairs to sold it in the world market.

There are many neologisms entering into our life. I gave some of them. Because Independence is introducing a lot of neologisms which could not be counted in one graduate work. I hope that I could give further development of the work later in my future research works.

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